

Equivalent Circuit Model to Simulate Neurostimulation by using Different Waveforms

Experimental Stimulation with Simulation Comparison

Diego Lujan Villarreal, Dietmar Schroeder and Wolfgang H. Krautschneider.

Institute of Nanoelectronics
Hamburg University of Technology
Hamburg, Germany

Abstract—A novel equivalent circuit model (ECM) has been developed to describe the nonlinear behavior of neurostimulation and to obtain a fundamental understanding concerning the magnitudes of the stimulation in the different layers of human tissue. The model includes all regions from the transcutaneous electrodes to the neuron cell membrane to simulate nerve stimulation with sinusoidal, linear increase and linear decrease waveforms. The model results of the potential across the electrodes are validated firstly by comparing their solution with experimental stimulation of the extensor muscles in the forearm of one subject, and secondly by assessing their correlation coefficient. The energy delivered by the device with the waveforms mentioned above is investigated for the dissipation in the human tissue layers. The frequency and current density dependency of the electrode-electrolyte, gel-skin interface and of the human tissue were considered.

Keywords- neurostimulation; strength-duration curve; electrical stimulation; skin impedance

I. INTRODUCTION

An equivalent circuit model is a necessity to analyze the impedance measurement of human tissue, the inhomogeneity of human skin and muscle, the anisotropy characteristics of muscle fibers, the non-linear phenomena of human skin [1], [2] and the time dependent ionic redistribution in the cell membrane.

The comprehensive equivalent circuit developed in our institute is extensively explained in [3] and it is shown in the three dimensional figure 1. The ECM includes a precise modeling of the circuit elements built as a series of ‘tissue subsystems’, hence these can be treated autonomously using electrical parameters and tissue thickness taken from literature. Further, it considers the dependency in the electrode-electrolyte gel-skin interfaces, the anisotropic characteristics of the muscle and the nonlinear behavior of the human skin.

The primary objective in this study is firstly to assess the agreement of the potential across the transcutaneous electrodes in experimental stimulation and in simulations, mainly using the strength-duration curve, with the waveforms stated above. To evaluate quantitatively their agreement, the correlation coefficient was utilized.

The second objective is to investigate the energy dissipation in the human tissue layers with the waveforms mentioned

above. The electrical properties of all human tissues considered in the model were taken from literature.

Thirdly, the energy and charge delivered by the stimulator device for the waveforms mentioned are compared with the results of the nowadays standard shape for electrical neurostimulation, the biphasic rectangular waveform [3].

Figure 1. Equivalent circuit model with the subsystems included. (Layer thicknesses not drawn to scale).

II. PARAMETERS IN SIMULATION

A. Electrode-electrolyte gel-skin equivalent circuit

The electrical properties of the electrode-electrolyte gel interface are dependent on frequency and current density and these can be measured using a balance bridge [4]. In this study, the gelled electrodes used were the same as in [3], therefore the same values of parameters R_B and C_B and R_{GEL} were utilized.

The frequency and current density parameters in the interface electrode-electrolyte gel can remain unchanged, regardless the day when the experiment is carried out. The half-cell potential, V_{hc} , was set to match the experimentally observed total DC offset of 3.4 V.

The parameters in the interface electrolyte gel-skin, R_{Gs} and C_{Gs} , depend strongly on the contact quality on the skin in different sessions of stimulation [3]. The frequency and current density components of the interface electrolyte gel-skin were adapted to match the peak voltage response in the stimulation experiment.

B. Skin, muscle and cell membrane parameters

The conductivity and permittivity which represent the tissues, namely σ_s and ϵ_s of the stratum corneum, σ_{LW} and ϵ_{LW} of the lower layers (all respectively), the longitudinal and transverse conductivity σ_{ML} and σ_{MT} of the muscle (all correspondingly), and the cell membrane electrical parameters are the same as [3]. A brief explanation in the importance of choosing correctly the electrical properties to determine the biological tissues is listed below.

The human tissue is a very inhomogeneous biological material. The frequency dependency or dispersion in the human tissue is significant. In a heterogeneous material, such as biological tissue, several dispersions can be observed and which are alpha (α), beta (β) and gamma (γ) [2].

At lower frequencies (in the range below several hundred kilohertz), the tissues exhibit alpha dispersion and which is caused by counterion polarization along the cell membrane. The physical interpretation of counterion polarization is reasonably simple and it depends on whether the ion sign is the same or opposite than of the ions in the counterion layer. Ions with the identical sign can enter to the counterion and the particle acts as a good conductor. Ions of opposite sign are excluded from the layer and must travel around the particle in the bulk electrolyte surrounding the particle. The charge is accumulated and the particle acts as an insulator and exhibits large permittivity.

The human tissue exhibits beta dispersion which is concentrated between 0.1 and 10MHz. In this frequency range, the cell membrane is charged through the intracellular and extracellular media. The beta dispersion is observable in both the permittivity and conductivity of the tissue.

Above 1 GHz, the tissue enters in gamma dispersion which is caused by the polarization of water molecules. For a detailed discussion of the dispersions and of the analysis in the characteristic frequency dependence plot of the permittivity and of the conductivity, see [5], [6].

Using the characteristic parallel equivalent circuit to represent biological materials, the dispersion in the human tissues has an important influence in the impedance, because the parallel capacitance becomes more important at high frequencies. As the capacitive impedance decreases with increasing frequency, current consequently flows throughout it and the impedance of the characteristic parallel combination decreases.

For long pulse durations, most of the current will therefore flow through the resistances. Thus, the conductivity dispersion has a significant effect in impedance simulations. At low frequencies, the impedance of the characteristic parallel circuit is therefore the sum of the resistances.

The skeletal muscle and bone are clearly anisotropic and frequency dependent. Muscle anisotropy arises mainly from the parallel arrangement of muscle fibers. Current flowing perpendicularly across the muscle fibers flows differently than that of flowing parallel to the fibers. The impedance of the transversal flow of the current is roughly five times greater than that of the longitudinal flow of current, in the direction of the muscle fiber [7].

III. METHODS AND MATERIALS

A. Subjects for experiment *In vivo*

The *in vivo* experiments were carried out under written consent of 1 healthy subject and conducted over six days. It was no background of neurological or of orthopedic disease history. Therefore, it was assumed that the desired muscle to stimulate was fully innervated.

B. Experimental Procedures

For the stimulation procedure and for the comparison of potential across the electrodes with simulations, the same stimulation setup and the experimental results described in [8] were utilized. The waveforms used in this study were sinusoidal, linear increase and linear decrease.

C. Simulation Procedure

From the stimulation results mentioned above, strength-duration curves were put together by finding the pulse widths and current amplitudes where the accelerometer reaction showed the minimum response. The evaluation was done for each single day, giving a total of eighteen curves, and corresponding means and standard deviations were computed.

For the respective pulse width, the longitudinal conductivity of the muscle, σ_{ML} , was varied in simulations such that the cell membrane voltage reaches threshold. The frequency and current density components of the interface electrolyte gel-skin were adapted to match the peak voltage response in the stimulation experiment. The magnitudes of the resistances R_{Gs} and C_{Gs} thus obtained are shown in Table 4 with all waveforms tested.

The thickness of every layer in the human tissues considered in the model was taken from literature [9], [10], [11], [12]. In order to simulate the change in the cell membrane potential of the extensor muscles in the forearm, the median and the radial nerves were firstly considered. By assessing the position of the electrodes, the median is deeper than the radial nerve and the simulation was carried out with only including the median nerve at a depth of 2.5 cm [13], [14] and assuming that the radial nerve will be consequently stimulated.

The charge transferred by the stimulator was calculated in each case by integrating the current over time. The energy dissipation in the skin and the energy delivered by the device

were obtained by integrating the multiplication of voltage and current over time. The correlation coefficient was found using a Matlab script.

IV. RESULTS

Figures 2 and 3 show the comparison of the voltage response peaks, positive and negative respectively, of biphasic rectangular pulse, sinusoidal, linear increase and linear decrease waveforms as average and standard deviation of the six days. The adaptation of the gel-skin impedance was done such that the error was evenly distributed between the positive and negative peak. The outcomes of biphasic rectangular pulse were taken from the results of [3] to show the voltage response comparison.

Figures 4 to 6 illustrate examples in the comparison of the mean potential across the electrodes in experimental stimulation and simulations as well as in the investigation of the delivered current and of the tissue potential drop with different waveforms.

Figure 7 illustrates the charge transferred by the stimulator. Figure 8 shows a comparison of the energy delivered by the device with all waveforms investigated. Figure 9 assesses the results of the energy dissipation in the human tissues with all waveforms tested.

The outcomes in the impedance of the gel-skin interface used to agree with the voltage response in stimulation experiments are shown in Table 4. Hatched cells in the table mean that the stimulator device could not stimulate the projected nerves and the extensor muscles.

TABLE I. VALUES USED TO MATCH THE VOLTAGE RESPONSE IN STIMULATION EXPERIMENTS.

<i>R_{Gs}</i> (k Ω)	1024 μ s	512 μ s	256 μ s	128 μ s
<i>RP</i>	6.01 \pm 1.54	5.64 \pm 1.92	2.12 \pm 0.4	0.518 \pm 0.067
<i>Sin.</i>	9.56 \pm 2.56	7.26 \pm 3.81	2.96 \pm 0.47	0.851 \pm 0.091
<i>L Inc.</i>	6.05 \pm 1.48	2.87 \pm 0.69	0.634 \pm 0.22	
<i>L Dec.</i>	9.25 \pm 3.84	8.93 \pm 3.41	4.58 \pm 0.813	

<i>C_{Gs}</i> (nF)	1024 μ s	512 μ s	256 μ s	128 μ s
<i>RP</i>	459 \pm 25.2	368 \pm 24.8	354 \pm 32.2	328 \pm 34.8
<i>Sin.</i>	392 \pm 20.4	362 \pm 20.1	324 \pm 28.9	319 \pm 31.4
<i>L Inc.</i>	418 \pm 26.4	398 \pm 33.6	358 \pm 34.4	
<i>L Dec.</i>	441 \pm 27.6	366 \pm 28.1	332 \pm 26.4	

<i>Imp.</i> (Ω)	1024 μ s	512 μ s	256 μ s	128 μ s
<i>RP</i>	355 \pm 19	222 \pm 16	115 \pm 10	62.2 \pm 6.6
<i>Sin.</i>	405 \pm 33	216 \pm 24	123 \pm 15	64.2 \pm 6.3
<i>L Inc.</i>	390 \pm 26	205 \pm 18	112 \pm 11	
<i>L Dec.</i>	369 \pm 23	223 \pm 17	123 \pm 9.7	

Outcomes of biphasic rectangular pulse referenced from [3]. Mean \pm SD. Pulse widths in the first row. RP: biphasic rectangular pulse, Sin: sinusoidal, L Inc.: linear increase, L Dec.: linear decrease.

The correlation coefficient was used to evaluate a quantitative relationship in the voltage response between simulations and experiments for the respective pulse widths

and for the waveforms investigated. Table 5 shows the results as mean and standard deviation for the six days.

TABLE II. CORRELATION COEFFICIENT RESULTS

	1024 μ s	512 μ s	256 μ s	128 μ s
<i>RP</i>	0.995 \pm 0.001	0.994 \pm 0.001	0.991 \pm 0.003	0.990 \pm 0.005
<i>Sin.</i>	0.996 \pm 0.0007	0.995 \pm 0.002	0.990 \pm 0.004	0.993 \pm 0.002
<i>L Inc.</i>	0.994 \pm 0.004	0.990 \pm 0.004	0.985 \pm 0.004	
<i>L Dec.</i>	0.995 \pm 0.001	0.994 \pm 0.004	0.990 \pm 0.001	

Outcomes of biphasic rectangular pulse referenced from [3]. Mean \pm SD.

V. DISCUSSION

Figures 2 and 3 show a strong agreement in the positive and negative voltage response peak, respectively, between ECM simulations and stimulation experiments. The variance of results in the voltage response in stimulation experiments are related to the differences in the tissue reaction of the subject in the sessions of stimulation.

The mean percentage error in the positive and negative voltage response peak of sinusoidal pulse reaches 0.7% and 7.7%, of linear increase achieves 0.4% and 1.5% and of linear decrease reaches 0.6% and 41.5%, all respectively. The high percentage error in the negative voltage response peak in linear decrease and sinusoidal pulse can be attributed to the low values of the negative voltage peak results in the stimulation experiments.

Figures 4 to 6 illustrate the strong agreement of the equivalent circuit model when not only the frequency and the current is changed but also when the waveform is modified. Due to the combination of their conductivity σ and permittivity ϵ , the tissue voltage drop reaches a few amount of volts compared with the total voltage response of the equivalent circuit.

The sum of the voltage drop in the stratum corneum, lower layers, muscle and nerve influences the energy dissipation in the tissues. The highest tissue voltage drop recorded in simulation was at 128 μ s with sinusoidal pulse by reaching 22.2%, followed by rectangular pulse by obtaining 16.9% of the voltage response in the electrodes. At 256 μ s, linear increase reached 16.9%, followed by linear decrease that obtained 16.4% of the voltage response in the electrodes. The remaining voltage drop can be attributed to the electrode-electrolyte gel-skin interfaces. The highest tissue voltage drop recorded in simulation also depends strongly on the delivered current to stimulate nerve and muscle.

Tissue injuries are related with a delivery of high current throughout the human tissues. By analyzing figure 7, it can be concluded that the risk of tissue damage is lower by using sinusoidal pulse at lower pulse widths. At 256 μ s, linear increase has the minimum charge delivered to the tissues. Sinusoidal pulse has the minimum charge delivered at high pulse widths, e.g. 1024 μ s. By comparing the results with biphasic rectangular pulse, a modification to sinusoidal pulse causes a 1.5-fold decrease at 1024 μ s.

Figures 2) to 9). 2) and 3) are the comparison with measurements of biphasic rectangular, sinusoidal, linear increase and linear decrease waveforms for different pulse widths: 2) Positive peak voltage response, 3) Negative peak voltage response. 4) to 6) are the voltage response comparison with: 4) 256 μ s linear decrease pulse, 5) 1024 μ s linear increase pulse and 6) 512 μ s sinusoidal pulse. The green plot corresponds to the delivered current in simulation and the magenta plot shows the simulated voltage drop from the stratum corneum to the cell membrane. 7) Mean and standard deviation of the charge delivered by the stimulator of all waveforms. 8) Mean and standard deviation of the energy delivered by the stimulator device of all waveforms. 9) Mean and standard deviation of the energy dissipation in the human tissues of all waveforms.

Energy-efficient stimulator devices deliver the minimum energy to the tissues and the energy delivered depends on the principle of the strength-duration curve, e.g. the frequency and the current used to reach action potential. Figure 8 displays the energy delivered by the stimulator device as mean and standard deviation for the six days. By analyzing the simulation results in figure 8, sinusoidal pulse is the energy-efficient waveform at high pulse widths, e.g. 1024 μs and also with lower pulse widths, e.g. 128 μs . By comparing the outcomes of biphasic rectangular pulse, an adaptation to sinusoidal pulse at 1024 μs causes a decrease by a factor of two. The energy delivered to the system is related not only to the interfaces electrode-electrolyte gel-skin but also to the energy dissipation of the human tissues.

The energy dissipation in the tissues can point toward the development of a portable energy-efficient stimulator device with safely delivered stimuli to the patients. Figure 9 shows the energy dissipation in the human tissues as mean and standard deviation for the six days. Compared to biphasic rectangular pulse, the sinusoidal pulse at 1024 μs produces only half of the energy dissipation. With respect to the optimal configuration in terms of the energy dissipation in the tissues, linear increase at 256 μs was found to be the optimal.

One aspect which is noteworthy to state is that the frequency dependent skin and muscle's longitudinal and transversal parameters are independent of the waveform. In other words, by maintaining fixed frequencies for stimulation and by changing the waveform, the skin and muscle parameters can remain unchanged.

VI. CONCLUSION

The equivalent circuit model developed in our institute reaches a strong agreement with stimulation experiments. The development of a comprehensive equivalent circuit model pursues a thorough verification of the potential drop and of the energy dissipation in the tissue layers considered.

The optimal waveform and pulse width in terms of the energy delivered by the device and of the energy dissipated in the tissues was found to be linear increase at 256 μs . As for the charge transferred by the device, sinusoidal pulse at 128 μs was found to be the optimal. With respect to the peak-to-peak voltage across the electrodes, linear decrease at 512 μs is the optimal configuration.

While the frequency and current density parameters in the interface electrode-electrolyte gel can remain unchanged, regardless the day when the experiment is carried out, the gel-skin interface parameters must be modified since the variation of the impedances reflects the variability of the contact quality on the skin when the electrodes were repeatedly attached on the distinct days of the stimulation experiments.

The independent aspect of the frequency dependent skin and muscle's longitudinal and transversal parameters when the waveform is changed gives our model a fast variation of parameters. The setting for stimulation such as the waveform used is independent from the internal behavior of the tissues.

The energy dissipation in the tissues can point toward the development of a portable energy-efficient stimulator device with safely delivered stimuli to the patients. By assessing the outcomes of biphasic rectangular pulse, an adaptation to sinusoidal pulse causes a decrease at higher pulses, e.g. 1024 μs by a factor of two, whereas at low pulses the energy dissipation has nearly the same result.

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